

Derivation of an equation to account for the Pallmann or soleconcentration effect

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An equation has been derived to account for the Pallmann effect on the assumption that when the particles of a sol collide with the electrode surface the diffuse electrical double layer surrounding each particle is distorted and the counter ions present in the distorted portion get an opportunity to record their activity on the reversible electrode. The fraction θ of the surface of the electrode covered by the distorted double layers of the colliding particles increases with their concentration, C , in the sol. It has been shown that $\theta = \frac{C}{K+C}$ where K is a constant. It is assumed that the number of counter ions associated with each particle does not change with dilution.

It has been pointed out that if $(H^+)_c$ be the activity of the counter ions indicated by the reversible electrode and $(H^+)_0$ that of the counter ions present, mainly as an impurity, in the intermicellar liquid then $(H^+)_c - (H^+)_0 = a\theta = \frac{aC}{K+C}$, where a is a proportionality constant. For a well-dialysed sol $(H^+)_0$ is small and when C is not too small $(H^+)_0$ may be neglected in comparison with $(H^+)_c$. The aforesaid equation can then be written as

$$\frac{1}{(H^+)_c} = \frac{1}{a} \left(1 + \frac{1}{K_0 C} \right) \text{ where } K_0 \text{ is a constant, or } (pH)_c = (p^a)_\infty + \log \left(1 + \frac{1}{K_0 C} \right).$$

The last equation has been found to agree well with facts.

It has been shown that the equations of Loosjes and Gupta can be deduced starting from the relation $\theta = \frac{C}{K+C}$.

It has also been pointed out that if E_0 and E_∞ are the values of E.M.F. indicated by the reversible electrode when the sol concentration $C = 0$ and $C = \infty$ respectively then the difference between E_0 and E_∞ should not be much smaller than the potential of the diffuse part of the double layer or ζ , the electrokinetic potential.

It has been observed by Pallmann¹ that as the concentration of the particles of H-clay in a sol or suspension is increased the H^+ ion activity of the sol measured by the potentiometric method increases. Bruyn² has found similar effect in the determination of I^- ion activity in negatively charged AgI sols. The aforesaid effect has been termed the Pallmann or sol concentration effect. It has also been investigated by Loosjes³ and Gupta⁴.

1. H. Pallmann, *Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1930, **30**, 354.
2. H. De Bruyn, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1942, **61**, 12; *ibid.*, 1942, **61**, 21.
3. R. Loosjes, *Colloid Sci.* Edited by Kruyt, Elsevier Publishing Co., 3rd reprint 1963, p. 185.
4. S. L. Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1956 **33**, 587.

Loosjes³ proposed the following equation to account for the aforesaid effect.

$$P_c^H - P_\infty^H = \frac{K}{C+K} (P_0^H - P_\infty^H) \quad \dots (1)$$

where P_0^H , P_c^H and P_∞^H represent the pH at sol concentration equal to zero, C and infinity respectively, K is a constant and C the sol concentration expressed in an arbitrary unit.

Loosjes equation (1) has been found to hold over a wide range of variation of C . Pallmann has also suggested a linear relation between C and H^+ ion activity, but for large values of C the equation does not agree with the experimental results. It appears from the literature that no satisfactory explanation of the Pallmann or sol concentration effect has been offered yet.

Gupta⁴ deduced the following equation ;

$$(H^+)^2 + K_1(H^+) = \alpha K_1 C \quad \dots (2)$$

where (H^+) and C represent the concentration of the H^+ ions and the colloidal particles respectively in the sol and K_1 and α are constants.

The deduction of equation (2) is based on the assumption that the H^+ ion activity due to the colloid is present in the intermicellar solution. The aforesaid assumption of Gupta⁴ does not appear to us to be valid for the reason that each colloidal particle is surrounded by a diffuse electrical double layer and the counter ions cannot go beyond the boundary of this double layer. In a well-dialysed sol the activity of the ions (cations and anions) is quite small in the intermicellar liquid (i.e. the liquid outside the boundaries of the diffuse double layers of the sol particles).

An equation for the Pallmann effect can, however, be derived on the basis of the mechanism suggested below :

When the negatively charged particles of a sol collide with the surface of the reversible electrode their electrical double layers are distorted and the counter ions present in the distorted portion of the double layer of each of the colliding particles get an opportunity to record their activity on the electrode. In the distorted portion of the double layer the ion squeezed between the surfaces of a colloidal particle and that of the electrode have much higher activity and, therefore, exert greater osmotic pressure than the ions in the intermicellar liquid and this tends to remove the colliding particle from the surface of the electrode. Besides, the reversible electrodes used are usually negatively charged and hence electrostatic force of repulsion also operates in expelling the colliding particles from the electrode surface.

It may also be pointed out that the concentration, n , of the counter ions increases exponentially within the double layer as the surface of the particle is approached according to the Boltzmann equation

$$n = n_0 \exp^{ze\psi_\delta/kT} \quad \dots (3)$$

where z represents the valencies of the counter ions, e the electronic charge and ψ_δ the potential (corresponding to n) of the diffuse part of the double layer, n_0 represents the concentration of the counter ions in the intermicellar liquid where $\psi_\delta = 0$.

For the sake of simplicity suppose that all the particles are of the same size and the colloid (say H-clay) is negatively charged. Let C be the concentration of the particles in the sol at which a fraction θ of the electrode surface is in contact with the distorted double layers of the particles. Then the rate at which the bare portion $(1-\theta)$ of the electrode comes in contact with the double layers of fresh particles is $K_1(1-\theta)C$ and the rate at which the particles are removed from the surface is $K_2\theta$ where K_1 and K_2 are the velocity constants. K_1 obviously depends on the diffusion constant and therefore varies as $1/\eta r$, η being the viscosity of the sol and r the radius of the particles. At equilibrium;

$$K_1(1-\theta)C = K_2\theta$$

solving for θ we get;

$$\theta = \frac{C}{C+K} \quad \dots (4)$$

where $K = K_2/K_1$.

It may be pointed out here that if the reversible electrode indicates $(H^+)_C$ as the H^+ ion activity at a concentration C of the sol then $(H^+)_C$ includes the activity of the H^+ ions in the distorted portions of the double layers which cover a fraction θ of the electrode surface and also the activity $(H^+)_0$ of the hydrogen ions in the intermicellar liquid. Hence $(H^+)_C - (H^+)_0$ must be proportional to θ . This can also be proved theoretically.

Therefore we may write

$$(H^+)_C - (H^+)_0 = a\theta = \frac{aC}{C+K} \quad \dots (5)$$

where a is a proportionality constant. The aforesaid deduction involves the assumption that the number of counter ions in the double layer of each particle does not change with dilution.

For a well-dialysed sol $(H^+)_0$ is small and if C is not too small, $(H^+)_0$ may be neglected in comparison with $(H^+)_C$. Therefore, equation (5) may be written as follows :

$$\frac{1}{(H^+)_C} = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{K}{aC} = \frac{1}{a} \left(1 + \frac{1}{K_0C} \right) \quad \dots (6)$$

where $K_0 = 1/K$.

It follows from equation (6) that a plot of $1/(H^+)_C$ against $1/C$ should be linear and from the intercept and slope of the line $1/a$ and $1/K_0$ can be found.

Equation (6) may also be written as :

$$(pH)_C = (p^a)_\infty + \log \left(1 + \frac{1}{K_0C} \right) \quad \dots (7)$$

where $(p^a)_\infty$ represents $\log 1/a$. Knowing $(p^a)_\infty$ and $1/K_0$ the values of $(pH)_C$ for different values of C , can be calculated from equation (7).

The equation of Gupta⁵ may be deduced in an approximate manner from equation (5). Neglecting $(H^+)_{0}$, equation (5) may be written as follows :

$$(H^+)_{C} = \frac{aC}{K+C} \quad \dots (8)$$

when C is small compared to K then $(H^+)_{C}$ varies as $\frac{a}{K} C$ or $C = \frac{K}{a} (H^+)_{C}$. Substituting this value of C in equation (8) we get

$$(H^+)_{C} = \frac{aC}{K + \frac{K(H^+)_{C}}{a}} \quad \dots (8a)$$

or

$$(H^+)_{C}[K + K(H^+)_{C}/a] = aC$$

or

$$[H^+]^2_{C} + K_1(H^+)_{C} = K_1\alpha C \quad \dots (8b)$$

where $K_1 = a$ and $\alpha = a/K$.

It may be noticed that equation (8b) is of the same form as equation (2) of Gupta.

Loosjes equation can also be derived from equation (4). At sol concentration, C , we may put θ as proportional to $(P^H)_{0} - (P^H)_{C}$.

$$\text{Therefore} \quad (P^H)_{0} - (P^H)_{C} = K'\theta \quad \dots (9)$$

As the sol concentration approaches infinity $(P^H)_{C}$ becomes $(P^H)_{\infty}$ and θ approaches unity.

$$\text{Therefore} \quad (P^H)_{0} - (P^H)_{\infty} = K' \quad \dots (9a)$$

Since θ is unity.

Substituting this value of K' in equation (9) and solving for θ , we get

$$\theta = \frac{(P^H)_{0} - (P^H)_{C}}{(P^H)_{0} - (P^H)_{\infty}} \quad \dots (9b)$$

Substituting this value of θ in equation (4) we get

$$\frac{(P^H)_{0} - (P^H)_{C}}{(P^H)_{0} - (P^H)_{\infty}} = \frac{C}{C+K} \quad \dots (9c)$$

or

$$1 - \frac{(P^H)_{0} - (P^H)_{C}}{(P^H)_{0} - (P^H)_{\infty}} = 1 - \frac{C}{C+K} \quad \dots (9d)$$

or

$$(P^H)_{C} - (P^H)_{\infty} = \frac{K}{K+C} [(P^H)_{0} - (P^H)_{\infty}] \quad \dots (10)$$

It will be noticed that equation (10) is identical with Loosjes equation (1).

5. A. Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **33**, 399.

It is to be noted that since K in equation (5) or K_0 in equation (7) involves the viscosity of the sol, the equations deduced above are expected to hold good so long as C is not so high that the sol develops plastic properties. In the following tables the results calculated from equation (7) are compared with those observed by Pallmann¹ and Chatterjee⁵.

The experimental data of Pallmann are recorded in the Tables I and II while the other tables contain Chatterjee's⁵ data.

TABLE I

Con. of sol C	$\frac{1}{C}$	Observed $(pH)_c$	Values of $(pH)_c$ calculated from		
			Pallmann eqn. (1)	Gupta's eqn. (2)	Author's eqn. (7)
40	0.025	5.10	5.07	5.05	5.11
50	0.02	5.02	4.99	4.95	5.02
75	0.0133	4.86	4.83	4.81	4.86
100	0.01	4.69	4.72	4.70	4.74
200	0.005	4.46	4.45	4.47	4.48
300	0.00333	4.32	4.26	4.34	4.36
400	0.0025	4.25	4.14	4.25	4.27
500	0.002	4.21	4.05	4.19	4.21
600	0.00167	4.19	3.97	4.13	4.17
700	0.00143	4.16	3.91	4.09	4.13

TABLE II

Constants in eqn. (1)		$H. Clay$	Constants in eqn. (7)		
$(PH)_0 = 5.87$			$(P^a)_\infty = 3.61$		
$(PH)_\infty = 3.74$			$\frac{1}{K_0} = 590$		
$K = 45$					
con. of sol C	$1/C$	Observed $(pH)_c$	Value of $(PH)_c$ calculated from		
			Loosjes eqn. (1)	Author's eqn. (7)	
37.8	0.0265	4.86	4.90	4.83	
50.0	0.02	4.72	4.75	4.71	
66.6	0.015	4.60	4.60	4.60	
100.0	0.01	4.47	4.40	4.45	
200.0	0.005	4.16	4.13	4.20	
400.00	0.0025	3.97	3.96	4.00	
800.0	0.00125	3.84	3.85	3.85	
2730.0	0.00037	3.82	3.77	3.70	

(Pasty mass)

TABLE III

Constants in eqn. (7)
 $(P^a)_\infty = 1.00,$ $1/K_0 = 58.$ K⁺-Clay

C in g/100	$1/C$	Observed (PK^+) _c	Calculated from eqn. (7) (PK^+) _c
16.96	0.059	1.70	1.65
9.955	0.100	1.78	1.83
7.324	0.0136	1.90	1.95
4.034	0.248	2.18	2.19
3.122	0.293	2.27	2.26
2.756	0.363	2.34	2.34
1.387	0.721	2.67	2.64
0.834	1.20	2.89	2.85
0.418	2.392	3.11	3.14

TABLE IV

Constants in eqn. (7)
 $(P^a)_\infty = 3.88;$ $1/K_0 = 11.2$ Ca⁺⁺-Clay

C in gram /100 g.	$1/C$	Observed (PCa^{++}) _c	Calculated from eqn.(7) (PCa^{++}) _c
6.088	0.164	4.35	4.33
3.143	0.318	4.54	4.54
2.123	0.471	4.68	4.68
1.289	0.776	4.84	4.86
0.278	3.600	5.54	5.50

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table I that the linear relation suggested by Pallmann¹ breaks down when C is above 200. The eqn. (7) deduced by the author fits the experimental data better than the equation of Gupta.

From Table II it appears that the equation of Loosjes and that of the author are in satisfactory agreement with the experimental data except when C is 2730. At this high value of C , the system is a pasty mass and as pointed out already under such conditions the equations are not expected to hold good.

From the data recorded in the Tables III and IV it will appear that the observed values of $(PK^+)_C$ and $(PCa^{++})_C$ are in fair agreement with those calculated from equation (7).

Attention may also be drawn to the fact that on the basis of the mechanism suggested above, to account for the sol concentration effect, the difference in the values of E.M.F., E_0 and E_∞ corresponding to $(P^H)_0$ and $(P^H)_\infty$ respectively, should not be much smaller than

the potential of the diffuse part of the double layer or ζ , the electrokinetic potential of the particles of H-clay and palmitic acid sols.

Therefore, we may write,

$$E_0 \sim E_\infty = \psi_s = \frac{kT}{Ze} \ln \frac{n}{n_0} = f\zeta \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

where f is a factor not much smaller than unity and the other terms are the same as in equation (3).

It is assumed here, that the electrical double layer is made up of two parts; the fixed-Stern⁶-Mukherjee⁷ layer and the mobile, diffuse layer. If ψ_s is identified with the potential of the diffuse part of the double layer then it will have the same value as ζ , the electrokinetic potential.

It may also be mentioned that somewhat similar conclusion was also drawn by Bruyn⁸ from his experiments on salt bridge effect and sol-boundary potential using AgI sols.

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7. J. N. Mukherjee, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1920-1921, **16**, 103.
8. H. De Bruyn, *Rec. Trav. Chem.*, 1946, **65**, 529.